

A Zero-Defect Manufacturing Decision-Support System for the Decorative Surfaced Panels Industry

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Abstract—Industry 4.0 technologies are increasingly driving the development of Zero-Defect Manufacturing (ZDM) solutions to reduce waste and enhance product quality. However, traditional ZDM methods face challenges in adaptability, real-world applicability, and handling data scarcity. This paper presents a cloud-based modular Decision-Support System (DSS) tailored for the decorative surfaced panels industry that incorporates real-time process monitoring, Machine Learning (ML), and Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) to proactively predict defects, identify root causes (e.g., temperature fluctuations), and recommend optimal machine parameters. Key innovations include a Zero-Shot Learning (ZSL) component for generating initial machine recipes for new panel types, reducing setup-phase waste, and Asset Administration Shells (AASs) for interoperable data communication. Evaluations demonstrate the DSS achieves a 90% F1-score in defect classification and reduces defect rates by 20 percentage points (pp) through parameter optimization. The architecture's modularity and integration with an industrial use case highlight its scalability and applicability across diverse manufacturing environments.

Index Terms—Decision-Support Systems, Machine Learning, Zero-Defect Manufacturing

I. INTRODUCTION

The manufacturing industry is shifting towards Zero-Defect Manufacturing (ZDM), driven by the need to minimize waste, enhance product quality, and meet stringent market demands. Traditional quality control methods, focusing on reactive defect detection and correction, are increasingly insufficient in addressing the complexities of modern production processes. Instead, ZDM emphasizes proactive strategies - prediction and prevention - to eliminate defects at their root, ensuring products meet specifications. This shifting paradigm aligns with Industry 4.0 principles, where advanced technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and real-time data analytics play pivotal roles in optimizing manufacturing systems.

Decision-Support Systems (DSSs) combine AI and ML to turn complex production data into useful information, improving the operator's decision-making process. DSSs boost operators' decisions by providing actionable insights, real-time recommendations, and explainable predictions, thereby enhancing decision-making without fully replacing human

judgment. However, despite these advantages, many DSSs face critical limitations: they often struggle to adapt to sudden process modifications (e.g., changes in material properties or equipment settings), inconsistent applicability in real-world scenarios using diverse industrial conditions, and lack of mechanisms to handle data scarcity.

This paper introduces a DSS for ZDM, developed as part of the EU-funded openZDM project, to improve the decorative surface panels production process. The proposed solution adopts a cloud-based modular architecture that integrates real-time process monitoring, data analytics enabling adaptive defect management, and Asset Administration Shells (AASs) for transparent data communication between components. By integrating ML models (e.g., Gradient Boosting, LSTM networks) with Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) techniques, the DSS predicts defects, identifies root causes (e.g., temperature fluctuations, pressure deviations), and recommends optimal machine parameters to operators via intuitive dashboards. The DSS also facilitates product development by using Zero-Shot Learning (ZSL) to generate initial machine recipes for new panel types, reducing setup-phase waste. In terms of performance, the DSS achieved 1) 90% F1-score classifying defects, and 2) an average reduction of 20 percentage points (pp) by using the recommended machine parameters. Those developments resulted in the following contributions:

- Adoption of an interoperable DSS architecture, with cloud-based modular deployment, that integrates real-time monitoring, model retraining functionalities enabling model updates, and AASs for enhanced data transparency.
- Usage of ZSL to streamline new product recipe recommendations, significantly reducing setup waste.
- Integration of the solution with an industrial use case demonstrating the DSS applicability and modularity.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II reviews ZDM strategies and DSS technologies, Section III details the decorative surface panels use case and the openZDM project, Section IV describes the system implementation, Section V presents experimental results, and Section VI concludes with future research directions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

ZDM strategies and DSSs are essential approaches for defect prediction and prevention. Key topics include proactive ZDM frameworks, DSS architectures aligned with Industry 4.0 principles, and the integration of ML and XAI to enhance defect management. The review synthesizes advancements in predictive modeling, parameter optimization, and human-centric decision-making, bridging theoretical algorithms with practical industrial applications.

A. Zero Defects Manufacturing

The ZDM concept provides a systematic approach to minimize and eliminate defects in production. Based on the principle of "doing things right the first time" [1], ZDM goes beyond traditional quality control by focusing not just on detecting and correcting defects but on proactively predicting and preventing them, aiming for complete elimination [2].

ZDM includes four main strategies: Detection, Repair, Prediction, and Prevention. Detection and Repair are reactive, involving actions taken after defects have occurred. Detection focuses on identifying defects, faults, and anomalies, categorizing them based on underlying causes. Repair involves reworking defective products whenever feasible once anomalies are detected. In contrast, Prediction and Prevention are proactive strategies. Prediction anticipates product quality by analyzing process data, while Prevention focuses on avoiding defect occurrence, typically by recommending corrective actions [1].

ZDM can be implemented through two approaches: product-oriented ZDM and process-oriented ZDM, as illustrated in Figure 1. Product-oriented ZDM targets defects at the product level, enabling early identification and preventing defective products from reaching customers. Contrarily, process-oriented ZDM focuses on monitoring and correcting defects in manufacturing equipment, which may allow defects to occur before detection [3]. Choosing between these two approaches impacts the efficiency and efficacy of defect management.

Fig. 1: ZDM product and process-oriented approaches (adapted from Psarommatis et al. [3]).

B. Decision Support Systems for ZDM

The integration of advanced technologies and human expertise is essential for the successful implementation of ZDM [4]. A human-centric ZDM approach incorporates both, ensuring that decision-making is enhanced rather than fully automated [5].

DSSs are powerful tools in this context, as they assist decision-makers by managing complex data, offering real-time analytics, and improving decision speed and accuracy [6]. Rather than replacing human operators, DSSs can enhance their capabilities, allowing informed decision-making while reducing cognitive load. This ensures consistent process monitoring and effective defect management without compromising production stability or efficiency [7].

C. Strategies for Defect Prediction

Prediction is the most common ZDM strategy in human-centric approaches [5], driven by advancements in AI, ML, and advanced analytics [8]. With high-quality data as the primary requirement, these methods have become applicable across various manufacturing contexts.

Common techniques include boosting algorithms such as Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM), XGBoost (XGB), and CatBoost, as well as Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), regression-based methods, and traditional classifiers like Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Naïve Bayes [9]–[15].

Classification is the preferred ML task to predict product quality [16]. Binary classification is preferred for defect prediction, as manufacturing data often lacks sufficient distinction for accurate multiclass classification [17]. Sensor data from production processes may be too similar across multiple defect types, making binary prediction a more robust approach.

D. Strategies for Defect Prevention

Prevention is essential for achieving long-term defect reduction in manufacturing. This strategy is usually implemented either directly, through optimization algorithms that recommend optimal production parameters, or indirectly by using interpretable ML models and XAI.

For indirect approaches, studies such as [11] demonstrate how SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) can help users recognize and, therefore, optimize adjustable production parameters that have a significant impact on final product quality. Similarly, [18] highlights the importance of integrating explainable methods to build operator trust in defect predictions, enabling actionable defect prevention measures.

Direct Prevention approaches use optimization methods like Nelder-Mead, Powell, Dual Annealing, and Basin Hopping to refine process settings by exploring parameter combinations [13], [17]. Other techniques include similarity searches using Euclidean distance to identify optimal conditions [19] or custom optimization algorithms tailored to specific manufacturing scenarios [20], [21].

III. DECORATIVE PANELS USE CASE

The use case description comprises two components: 1) an overview of the openZDM project and 2) the introduction of a practical validation scenario. The project overview clarifies how the developed solution integrates with the openZDM framework. Complementing this, the industrial validation scenario - demonstrated through the decorative surfaced panels manufacturing use case - serves to validate the practical applicability of the developed DSS.

A. openZDM Project

The openZDM project¹ is an EU-funded Innovation Action that is developing an open platform to achieve ZDM across various production environments. It integrates non-destructive inspection methods and data-driven quality assessment techniques [8] to enable proactive defect detection and process adaptation. By continuously analyzing sensor data and ML insights, the openZDM platform provides timely recommendations for adjusting process parameters and reducing defects, waste, and downtime while improving overall production efficiency and sustainability.

The validation of the openZDM platform is through five industrial pilots spanning a diverse range of sectors, including steel parts manufacturing, automotive assembly, electric vehicle battery production, glass bottle production, and decorative panels manufacturing.

B. Decorative Surfaced Panels Manufacturing

Part of the process for manufacturing the decorative panels consists of coating the raw particle panels with impregnated decorative papers and then pressing them under controlled temperature and pressure to form high-quality panels with attractive, durable surfaces. The process, in Figure 2, requires precise control over factors like resin concentration, drying times, and pressing conditions, as even slight deviations can lead to visible surface defects, such as misaligned layers, or surface irregularities, that compromise both aesthetics and structural integrity. Maintaining a high level of quality in this production process is critical to minimizing waste, ensuring consistency, and meeting stringent market demands.

Fig. 2: Press and produced panel.

The openZDM project is set to transform this manufacturing process by proactively predicting defects before they occur, explaining the underlying causes using XAI, and providing real-time recommendations on machine parameter adjustments to prevent the emergence of defects.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation of the DSS focuses on its architecture, modules, and integration with the panel production line. Figure 3 illustrates the integration between the factory shop floor and the cloud-based platform. The modular architecture combines real-time data monitoring via Microsoft Azure, AASs for data interoperability, and Docker containers for scalable deployment. The modules included in the DSS are: 1) a defect prediction module employing ML and SHAP-based explanations, 2) a defect prevention mechanism using optimization algorithms to minimize defects, and 3) a ZSL component for generating initial machine recipes for new product types, reducing setup-phase waste.

A. Integrated Architecture

Looking into detail, the integration between the manufacturing process and the openZDM platform has the following steps: 1) monitoring real-time data from the production process using the Microsoft Azure legacy system, 2) execution of the DSS, computing the defect prediction, explanation, and parameters recommendation (defect prevention), and 3) results visualization, notifying the operator about the new disruption. The openZDM platform monitors the manufacturing process by subscribing to Microsoft Azure. Every variable update is recorded in the digital representation using an AAS. When a new panel enters the process, it triggers the defect prediction algorithm, which estimates the defect probability and, in case of a higher risk of defect, provides 1) a recommendation of machine parameters to avoid/minimize the risk and 2) a defect explanation.

The AAS is a digital representation of a physical asset encapsulating its data, functions, and interfaces [22]. For that use case, the AAS adopts a type 2 AAS, capturing and aggregating real-time information from the production process without directly controlling the asset. The AAS aggregates information about sensor and process data, including machine speed, pressure, or temperature. As a structured data sample representing the last process state, the AAS facilitates data ingestion by the DSS and other services. Consequently, using a type 2 AAS enhances transparency across the digital and physical components and supports informed decision-making.

The deployment of the openZDM platform was located in the cloud, using Docker as a containerization engine, increasing modularity and facilitating the installation process. Each module was deployed within a Docker container, including the DSS, the dashboards, and the orchestration module. The DSS includes defect prediction, explanation, machine parameters optimization, and new product recipe recommendation algorithms. The Docker container with the DSS communicates using HTTP as protocol and JSON as data format. The data

¹<https://www.openzdm.eu/>

Fig. 3: openZDM platform integration with shop floor and DSS.

format followed the AAS structure, allowing interoperable communication. The HTTP methods include the following:

- **Predict Defect:** Method that receives a data sample from the production process and computes the defect prediction and explanation, and in case of higher risk of defect, provides the machine recommendation parameters as a prevention action.
- **Train Model:** Module for training the defect prediction model with the most recent data. The method uses as inputs the features and target names (for retrieving the tables with the training data) and the training parameters, and obtains a trained model used for defect prediction.
- **Performance Monitor:** Function used to obtain the performance of the defect prediction model on the last production order. The adopted performance metric is the difference (error) between the real defect ratio of the production order and the one from the prediction model.
- **Test Product:** Method capable of providing optimized initial recommendations of machine parameters for new panel types, avoiding large amounts of waste generated during the setup phase.

B. Defect Prediction & Explanation

The first module of the DSS is the defect prediction algorithm, which classifies potential defects in panels using an ML model trained offline on historical data from 2022 to 2024. The model performs two classification tasks. A binary classifier is used to determine whether a panel has a defect. If a defect is present, a subsequent multiclass classifier identifies the specific defect type. As mentioned before, an HTTP service was implemented to enable real-time defect detection. This service hosts the trained model and processes incoming API requests, receiving a single sample with the panel data at each time. The service then returns a prediction, indicating whether the panel is likely to have a defect, along with the associated probability. In addition to returning the defect code, the model explains the prediction by identifying the most

influential variables for that decision. This is achieved using SHAP values, which quantify the contribution of each feature to the final prediction. The service computes the top three most important variables for each sample, helping operators understand which factors played a key role in determining the defect classification. Both defect prediction indicators (defect code, probability, timeline, and last execution) and explanation (three most important variables) are presented to the operator in a dashboard, as illustrated in Figure 4.

As the service runs, it continuously tracks the number of predicted defects, associating them with the production order code. After a period of operation, the system allows operators to input the actual number of defective panels for a specific production order. This value is compared with the model's predictions, and the system returns the discrepancy error, helping operators assess whether the model requires retraining to improve its accuracy.

The model pipeline includes processing steps applied to ensure data quality and improve model performance. First, it filters invalid entries by removing/ignoring samples with missing or irrelevant values, such as when the production line was inactive, or defect codes were invalid. The process of feature selection was performed by dropping non-informative columns, such as textual descriptions and unnecessary metadata, to reduce noise. Categorical features with limited unique values were transformed into numerical representations to make them suitable for ML algorithms. Missing data was handled by removing incomplete entries, ensuring the data remained clean and consistent. Correlation analysis was done to identify and eliminate highly correlated features, preventing redundancy and improving model efficiency.

C. Defect Prevention

The DSS incorporates a machine parameter optimization mechanism to reduce/prevent defect occurrences. When the model predicts a sample has a defect, an optimization algorithm is triggered to recommend parameter adjustments for the

Fig. 4: Defect prediction (left side) and explanation (right side), with sensitive data blurred (variable names and defect types).

machine, aiming to improve production quality. This optimization process leverages historical data, identifying past machine settings that resulted in lower defect rates. The algorithm compares the real-time sample’s machine parameters with those of previously successful runs and computes an optimal adjustment. The algorithm defines upper and lower bounds for each machine parameter based on historical training data to achieve this. It then applies a constrained optimization process using the L-BFGS-B method to find the closest parameters that would likely reduce defects. The recommended parameter set is denormalized to the machine’s operational scale and presented to operators as a suggested adjustment to improve manufacturing quality. By integrating this optimization capability, the system predicts defects and provides actionable insights for reducing their occurrence, enriching production efficiency and quality control.

D. New Product Recipe Recommendation

When new types of panels are introduced in the manufacturing process, the machinery requires an initial setup phase where different parameters are tested to find the optimal recipe for production. Usually, the setup phase generates large amounts of defective panels and waste because the operator tests different parameters to find the optimal recipe. The DSS aims to reduce the waste generated during the setup phase by providing an optimized machine parameters recipe, avoiding having extended tests of parameters. For that, it integrates a ZSL model [23] capable of, given the panel’s characteristics, providing an initial recommendation of machine parameters and the defect ratio associated with that recipe.

The ZSL component comprises two models: 1) a regression model that, given the panel characteristics and machine parameters, estimates the defect ratio, and 2) an optimizer that experiments, using the regression model, with different machine parameters (for fixed panel characteristics) to obtain the ones minimizing the defect ratio. The implemented optimization approach is based on the Dual Annealing algorithm, which iteratively explores different machine parameter combinations. At each iteration, it uses the regression model’s estimations to guide its search. Once the optimization process has ended, the

optimizer outputs both the optimal machine parameters and the corresponding estimated defect ratio.

V. EXPERIMENTS & RESULTS

The experimental validation of the DSS evaluates its predictive accuracy, real-time monitoring efficacy, and impact on product development. Key findings include: 1) a comparative analysis of the ML models (e.g., AdaBoost, XGBoost) for defect prediction, with ensemble methods achieving superior performance, 2) online monitoring results demonstrating low and stable defect ratio error, confirming the system’s reliability in dynamic production environments, and 3) the ZSL component’s success in reducing setup-phase waste through optimized recipe recommendations for new panel types.

A. Defect Prediction & Prevention Performance

The classification of panel defects was performed using multiple ML models, as described previously. As shown in the Table I, among the evaluated techniques, AdaBoost, Gradient Boosting, and XGBoost achieved the highest performance, each obtaining an F1-score of 0.8893, along with high precision (0.9039), recall (0.8895), and accuracy (0.8904) values. These ensemble-based methods effectively captured relevant patterns in the data, leading to superior predictive performance. Additionally, LSTM models were explored due to their ability to capture temporal dependencies, which seemed promising given the time-series nature of the data. However, their performance was significantly lower (F1-scores of 0.5266 for TensorFlow and 0.3842 for PyTorch). The poor performance is primarily due to the API calls processing data sequentially, preventing the model from leveraging temporal dependencies across multiple panels, thereby reducing its advantage over traditional models. Among the top-performing models, XGBoost was selected for deployment in the service, as it offers the fastest evaluation time compared to AdaBoost and Gradient Boosting while maintaining the same level of predictive performance. This efficiency makes it more suitable for real-time or large-scale applications.

The optimization mechanism was tested across the entire test dataset. Applying the recommended parameter adjustments for samples predicted to be defective, leading to an

TABLE I: Defect prediction models' performance comparison.

Model	Precision	Recall	Accuracy	F1-Score
AdaBoost	0.9039	0.8895	0.8904	0.8893
Decision Tree	0.9033	0.8875	0.8883	0.8871
Extra Trees	0.8828	0.8711	0.8719	0.8708
Gradient Boosting	0.9039	0.8895	0.8904	0.8893
KNN	0.5385	0.5327	0.5344	0.5153
Logistic Regression	0.6325	0.6055	0.6075	0.5855
MLP	0.4889	0.4897	0.4885	0.4795
Random Forest	0.9006	0.8868	0.8876	0.8865
XGBoost	0.9039	0.8895	0.8904	0.8893
LSTM (Tensorflow)	0.6774	0.4307	0.6163	0.5266
LSTM (Pytorch)	0.7854	0.2543	0.5961	0.3842

average improvement of 20 pp in the probability of the sample being classified as non-defective.

B. Online Monitoring

Evaluating the DSS performance should consider not only offline tests (using training and test data) but also online evaluation. The online evaluation occurs after the production of an order, comparing the real number of defective panels (assessed by the operator) with the number of defect predictions. For that, the openZDM platform calls the model performance HTTP method, with the information about the production order ID, number of produced panels, and number of defective panels, and receives the number of predicted defects and total predictions, the percentage of predicted defects and real defects, and the defect ratio error.

Equation 1 reflects the defect ratio error (E_{DR}) formula calculation for online evaluation of the defect prediction model. The E_{DR} results from the absolute difference between two ratios: the actual defect percentage of the production order (ratio between defective panels (D_{panels}) and total number of produced panels (N_{panels})) and the predicted defect percentage (ratio between the number of predicted defects (D_{pred}) and the total number of predictions (N_{pred})).

$$E_{DR} = \left| \frac{D_{panels}}{N_{panels}} - \frac{D_{pred}}{N_{pred}} \right| \quad (1)$$

The low and stable E_{DR} values demonstrated the DSS's ability to generalize to dynamic production conditions while maintaining accuracy over time. The tracking of predicted and actual defect rates fostered operator trust in the system's recommendations, enabling proactive defect management. This alignment reduced unnecessary manual inspections and accelerated root-cause analysis, contributing to waste reduction and enhanced production efficiency.

C. Product Development Performance

The regression model developed to estimate the defect ratio (ranging between 0% and 100%), based on panel characteristics and machine parameters, was implemented using a Random Forest Regressor. Consistent with the previously discussed modules, the model was trained on historical data collected between 2022 and 2024 and tested on a separate subset of the same dataset. Performance evaluation was based

on MSE and the Coefficient of Determination (R^2), achieving an MSE of 0.024 and an R^2 of 0.901, demonstrating a high level of predictive accuracy.

TABLE II: Example of comparison between real machine parameters and the generated recommended values for a new product recipe.

Machine Parameter ID	Real Value	Recommended Value
mp00	2200.0	2200.0
mp01	1.0	1.0
mp02	0.2	0.2
mp03	29.0	27.0
mp04	3000.0	3000.0
mp05	1000.0	1000.0
mp06	14.0	13.0
mp07	186.0	186.0
mp08	12.5	11.3
mp09	1200.0	1200.0
mp10	350.0	350.0
mp11	55.0	55.0
mp13	11.9	11.9
mp14	152.0	150.0
mp15	45.0	40.0
mp16	16.0	16.0
mp17	0.0	0.0
mp18	191.0	191.0

The second step of the ZSL algorithm involves the optimizer developed to identify the optimal machine parameters that, for a given set of fixed panel characteristics, minimize the defect ratio. To evaluate its performance, a subset of the testing data was used, specifically the samples with an actual defect ratio of 0%. For each of these, the optimizer took the fixed product characteristics and generated the machine parameters expected to achieve the same defect-free result. These recommended parameters were then compared to the original ones, and, in most cases, the recommended values closely matched the real ones. Table II illustrates, for a sample with a defect ratio of 0%, the comparison between the real machine parameters and the optimal parameters generated, both of which estimate a defect ratio of 0%.

VI. CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

This paper presented a cloud-based, modular DSS designed to improve ZDM within the decorative surfaced panels industry. By integrating real-time monitoring, ML (specifically XGBoost for optimal performance), XAI using SHAP, and AASs for interoperability, the system successfully addresses defect prediction, root cause explanation, and machine parameter optimization. Key achievements include a high defect classification accuracy (90% F1-score), a significant reduction in defect probability (20 pp) through parameter recommendations, and an effective ZSL component for generating initial recipes for new products, thereby minimizing setup waste. The successful deployment and online monitoring in an industrial use case validated the system's practical applicability, modularity, and ability to enhance production efficiency and quality control by providing actionable, data-driven insights.

Future efforts aim to integrate the DSS with a machine vision module designed to assist operators in defect detec-

tion. By analyzing real-time camera feeds, the system would flag potential defects (e.g., scratches), highlighting them for operator review. This approach minimizes fatigue, allowing operators to focus on root-cause analysis and corrective actions. The vision system would integrate seamlessly with the existing DSS, providing visual evidence to support AI-driven predictions and recommendations. This human-AI collaboration aligns with the openZDM philosophy of augmenting expertise, ensuring operators retain oversight while leveraging automation for efficiency.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B. Caiazzo, M. D. Nardo, T. Murino, A. Petrillo, G. Piccirillo, and S. Santini, "Towards zero defect manufacturing paradigm: A review of the state-of-the-art methods and open challenges," *Computers in Industry*, vol. 134, 1 2022.
- [2] D. Powell, M. C. Magnanini, M. Colledani, and O. Myklebust, "Advancing zero defect manufacturing: A state-of-the-art perspective and future research directions," *Computers in Industry*, vol. 136, 4 2022.
- [3] F. Psarommatis and G. May, "A systematic analysis for mapping product-oriented and process-oriented zero-defect manufacturing (zdm) in the industry 4.0 era," *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, vol. 15, 2023.
- [4] F. Psarommatis, G. May, and V. Azamfirei, "Zero defect manufacturing in 2024: a holistic literature review for bridging the gaps and forward outlook," 2024.
- [5] P. K. Wan and T. L. Leirmo, "Human-centric zero-defect manufacturing: State-of-the-art review, perspectives, and challenges," *Computers in Industry*, vol. 144, 1 2023.
- [6] N. A. Q. M. Shafee, E. Mohamad, M. S. A. Rahman, M. K. H. M. Zaidi, T. Ito, and O. Oktavianty, "How well do decision support systems help decision makers? an examination of adopting lean manufacturing processes," 2024.
- [7] P. Brauner, A. C. Valdez, R. Philipsen, and M. Ziefle, "Defective still defective – how correctness of decision support systems influences user's performance in production environments," in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, vol. 9752. Springer Verlag, 2016, pp. 16–27.
- [8] P. Catti, A. Freitas, E. Pereira, G. Gonçalves, R. P. Lopes, N. Nikolakis, and K. Alexopoulos, "Data analytics and ai for quality assurance in manufacturing: Challenges and opportunities," in *Learning Factories of the Future*, S. Thiede and E. Lutters, Eds. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024, pp. 205–212.
- [9] H. Tiensuu, S. Tamminen, O. Haapala, and J. Röning, "Intelligent methods for root cause analysis behind the center line deviation of the steel strip," *Open Engineering*, vol. 10, pp. 386–393, 1 2020.
- [10] H. Tiensuu, S. Tamminen, E. Puukko, and J. Röning, "Evidence-based and explainable smart decision support for quality improvement in stainless steel manufacturing," *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, vol. 11, 11 2021.
- [11] J. Takalo-Mattila, M. Heiskanen, V. Kyllonen, L. Maatta, and A. Bogdanoff, "Explainable steel quality prediction system based on gradient boosting decision trees," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 68 099–68 110, 2022.
- [12] K. C. Demirel, A. Şahin, and E. Albey, "A web-based decision support system for quality prediction in manufacturing using ensemble of regressor chains," in *Communications in Computer and Information Science*, vol. 1255 CCIS. Springer, 2020, pp. 96–114.
- [13] R. C. Dias, P. P. Senna, A. F. Gonçalves, J. Reis, N. Michalaros, K. Alexopoulos, and M. Gomes, "Prefab framework - product quality towards zero defects for melamine surface boards industry," in *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 54. Elsevier B.V., 2021, pp. 570–575.
- [14] M. Kulisz, K. Antosz, and E. Kozłowski, "Integration of statistical analysis and machine learning techniques for enhanced quality control in candle oil cartridge manufacturing," in *Lecture Notes in Mechanical Engineering*. Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH, 2024, pp. 376–387.
- [15] K. Deshpande, J. Holzweber, S. Thalhuber, A. Hämmerle, M. Mayrhofer, A. Pichler, and P. L. de Paula Filho, "Manufacturing line ablation, an approach to perform reliable early prediction," in *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 232. Elsevier B.V., 2024, pp. 752–765.
- [16] Z. Kang, C. Catal, and B. Tekinerdogan, "Machine learning applications in production lines: A systematic literature review," *Computers and Industrial Engineering*, vol. 149, 11 2020.
- [17] B. Coutinho, E. Pereira, and G. Gonçalves, "0-dmf: A decision-support framework for zero defects manufacturing," in *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Informatics in Control, Automation and Robotics - Volume 1: ICINCO, INSTICC*. SciTePress, 2024, pp. 253–260.
- [18] S. Tamminen, H. Tiensuu, E. Ferreira, H. Helaakoski, V. Kyllönen, J. Jokisaari, and E. Puukko, "From measurements to knowledge - online quality monitoring and smart manufacturing," in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, vol. 10933 LNAI. Springer Verlag, 2018, pp. 17–28.
- [19] J. D. J. Schmitt, "Similarity search and prediction based process parameter adaptation for quality improvement in interlinked manufacturing processes," 2018.
- [20] I. T. Christou, N. Kefalakis, J. K. Soldatos, and A. M. Despotopoulou, "End-to-end industrial iot platform for quality 4.0 applications," *Computers in Industry*, vol. 137, 5 2022.
- [21] F. Psarommatis and D. Kiritis, "A hybrid decision support system for automating decision making in the event of defects in the era of zero defect manufacturing," *Journal of Industrial Information Integration*, vol. 26, 3 2022.
- [22] K. Wei, J. Z. Sun, and R. J. Liu, "A review of asset administration shell," in *2019 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management (IEEM)*, 2019, pp. 1460–1465.
- [23] E. Pereira, J. Reis, R. J. F. Rossetti, and G. Gonçalves, "A zero-shot learning approach for task allocation optimization in cyber-physical systems," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Cyber-Physical Systems*, vol. 2, pp. 90–97, 2024.